

Electronic Theory of Valency and the Constitution of Aromatic Diazo Compounds.

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Though the diazo compounds were discovered in 1858 by Peter Griess and the utility of these in synthetic organic chemistry and in the chemistry of dyestuffs have been thoroughly exploited, the problem regarding their constitution still remains an open one.

It is needless to recall the details of controversy or the many mistakes and retractions made on both sides of the rival schools of thought.

Stereoisomerism was all along advocated by Hantzsch and his pupils whilst the structural isomerism was upheld by no less authorities than Blomstrand, Jacobson, V-Meyer, von Pechmann and Bamberger. Universal agreement has been reached by both the schools regarding the diazonium compounds. Blomstrand's formula $\begin{matrix} \phi \\ \text{X} \end{matrix} \rangle \text{N} \equiv \text{N}$ being accepted and that of Kekulé, *viz.*, $\phi - \text{N} = \text{N} - \text{X}$ being rejected (where ϕ stands for benzene nucleus and X for strong electro-negative elements like the halogens).

The bone of contention is the explanation of the isomeric diazo compounds.

Defects of Hantzsch's Views.

(i) Stereoisomers, in general, resemble one another very closely in chemical properties, whereas the *syn*- and *anti*-compounds of Hantzsch differ very markedly.

(ii) Close resemblance of *syn* with diazonium compounds, their instability and explosive character, led Hantzsch to assume that in many cases, *syn* behaves as a pseudo-diazonium—equilibrium exists

between them not only in solution but solid solutions of the two are frequent.

(iii) The difference in the absorption spectra of *syn*- and *anti*-diazotates of potassium.

Angeli from his studies of isomeric unsymmetrical azoxy compounds, came to the conclusion that the *normal* and *iso*-diazotates are structural isomers, the corresponding ions having the formulæ

(iv) According to the rival school, Hantzsch has not been able to prove satisfactorily that the isomeric non-electrolytic diazo-cyanides as well as the diazo-sulphonates are true stereoisomers, cyanides and sulphites themselves having tautomeric structures

Defects of the Structural Formula so far advocated.

(i) The main and the gravest objection is that the normal diazotate of potassium is formulated exactly as the diazonium hydroxide, whence it follows that once we are to assume diazonium hydroxide as a strong base and again as a weak acid.

(ii) Existence of the three isomeric diazo-cyanides from *p*-anisidine obtained by Hantzsch, namely,

Colourless soluble
electrolyte.

Labile coloured non-electrolyte.

Stable coloured non-
electrolyte.

was regarded by Hantzsch himself and his supporters as a very strong proof of his stereochemical theory since Bamberger's structural theory could only account for two of them.

A critical examination of the theories so far put forward reveals that

(a) In diazonium salts there is a triple bond between two $\bar{\text{N}}$ atoms, one being pentavalent and the other trivalent.

(b) In diazo compounds regarding the accepted Hantzsch-Kekulé formula, there is a double bond between the two $\bar{\text{N}}$ atoms, both being trivalent.

We think this is the main reason why "syn" and diazonium compounds resemble one another so much.

The very disproportionate (unequal) sharing of electrons between two N atoms is the real cause of the instability of "syn" compounds.

We consider that the structural formulæ based on electronic theory of valency as advocated in this paper can meet with all the objections raised by Hantzsch against structural theory.

Electronic theory can predict the following cases :

(i) When X is strongly electronegative and when the electropositivity of the $C_6H_5N_2$ -group is augmented by the substitution of Me or OMe in the *ortho*-position of the benzene nucleus, only diazonium compounds will be formed.

(ii) When X is weakly electronegative or when the electropositivity of $C_6H_5N_2$ -group is diminished by the substitution of Br, NO_2 , etc., in the *ortho* or *para*-position of the benzene nucleus, diazo compounds will result.

Hantzsch assumes that the "normal salts with strong (mineral) acids are in the solid state, mainly diazonium but partly (especially the halides) solid solutions of diazonium and *syn*-diazo; in solution they give almost entirely the diazonium ions. These can now be better explained by the deformation theory of Fajans and on the idea of easy conversion of co-valent "syn" compounds to electrovalent diazonium compounds.